

F. O. Chernenkov, O. A. O. Mustafa

Benefits of Big Data in the Financial Sector and Financial Stability Risks

KEYWORDS

big data,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The use of big data in the financial sector is relevant for enhancing operational efficiency, risk management, fraud prevention, and customer experience.

This study is aimed at providing a theoretical conceptualization of big data, identifying its benefits, and assessing the risks associated with its adoption by financial institutions.

Materials and methods. The materials used in the study were as follows: peer-reviewed journal publications in finance, economics, and data analytics; reports from financial institutions and consulting firms on big data applications in finance. When processing information, methods of theoretical analysis, classification, and synthesis were used.

Results. It has been revealed that big data allows for enhanced analytical research quality, predictive modeling of economic trends and market fluctuations, comprehensive market dynamics analysis, medical data analytics for improved diagnostics and treatment selection, predictive maintenance in manufacturing through sensor data analysis, development of socio-economic programs at governmental levels, fraud and corruption detection in financial systems, etc. The analysis substantiates both the rapid evolution of big data technologies and their strategic value for financial sector applications. Through literature review, the authors propose a novel definition of big data technology specific to financial institutions, incorporating distinctive features and advantages relevant to this sector. Examination of current big data implementations in finance reveals core benefits alongside existing limitations of these technologies.

Conclusion. Big data applications in finance contribute to process optimization and cost reduction, advanced risk management capabilities, personalized service offerings, fraud detection and prevention, regulatory compliance enhancement. These technologies facilitate more accurate market trend forecasting and data-driven decision making.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, all sectors of the economy are undergoing active digitalization and implementing various information technologies that enable customers to receive fast and high-quality financial services, reduce costs through innovative, flexible and adaptable technological solutions, create new human resource management tools, increase labor productivity, minimize errors, etc. The crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 accelerated the digital transition and reinforced the pre-existing trend toward digitalization, which was already associated with the use of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data [1]. Typically, crisis periods are associated with a decline in investments in long-term innovative technological projects; however, in 2020, a completely different trend emerged – an increase in investments by the banking sector in big data processing technologies.

The investment boom was driven by the mass transition to remote work, increased demand for digital technologies during quarantine (particularly contactless payments), efforts of financial institutions to maximize the automation of their business processes and customer interaction mechanisms to improve efficiency, and the intensified use of e-commerce by sellers and marketplaces, online stores, and delivery services by consumers. As a result, people began using their gadgets, phones, tablets, and other electronic devices more frequently, contributing to a rapid increase in the volume of big data [2].

With the development and rapid spread of the Internet, the total amount of information it contains is growing every second at an unprecedented rate. Humanity has already entered the era of big data and information. Consequently, people now have access to a vast resource such as big data which enables higher-quality analytical research, the creation of models for predicting economic trends and market changes, the study of market dynamics, the analysis of medical data to improve diagnostics and treatment selection, the prediction of equipment failures in production through sensor data analysis, the development of social and economic programs at the state level, and the detection of fraud and corruption in the financial sector, among other applications. Artificial intelligence, which operates on big data, is used in various fields, including information systems, machine translation, telecommunications, and transportation [3].

Thus, the relevance of analyzing the benefits of big data in the financial sector stems from the fact that modern financial institutions generate and process vast

amounts of data. The effective use of big data can improve decision-making processes, optimize operations, and improve the level of customer service. Based on big data analytics, financial institutions gain several advantages, such as better understanding customer needs in trade, assessing credit risks in banking services, and employing effective algorithms to detect and prevent financial crimes and fraud in information security.

All of the above explains the relevance of the research topic and the feasibility of using big data technology in the financial sector.

This study is aimed at providing a theoretical understanding of the essence of big data and identifying the benefits and risks associated with its use by financial institutions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included scientific publications and studies in the fields of finance, economics, and data analysis published in peer-reviewed journals (Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Annals of Data Science, Soft Computing, Journal of Data, Information and Management, Future Business Journal, SN Business & Economics, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, Journal of Electrical Systems and Information Technology, Review of Managerial Science).

The study also incorporated reports from financial institutions and consulting firms on big data applications in the financial sector, along with market research findings regarding the current state of financial technology development and industry challenges.

When processing information, the methods of theoretical analysis, classification, and generalization were used.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A significant number of scientific papers are devoted to the use of big data in the financial sector, enabling analysis of vast information volumes for risk management, fraud prevention, service personalization, and algorithmic trading, and thereby enhancing operational efficiency and security.

K. N. A. Arthur and R. Owen examine management challenges, ethical considerations, and operational issues related to big data acquisition, manipulation, and commercialization in financial services [4].

S. Norikumo notes that the history of data management in the financial sector is relatively long compared to other industries; however, current practices demonstrate inadequate data utilization. The author analyzes optimal data governance frameworks for financial institutions and projects future developments in financial information systems [5].

G. Pisoni et al. argue that in today's rapidly evolving financial industry, knowledge management and data-driven decision-making have become essential to the success of financial technology companies. The authors demonstrate how technological advancements enable financial institutions to develop innovative services [6].

J. Soldatos et al. highlight that there is still no standardized and straightforward way to design, deploy, and operate data-intensive systems for digital finance. The authors present complementary perspectives on architectural models, including logical representations and application deployment considerations aligned with reference architectures [7].

S. Patel and M. Shah et al. investigate big data adoption in audit processes, concluding its implementation lags behind comparable industries [8].

J. Xiao advocates for analyzing deficiencies in financial audit risk prevention and proposes specific mitigation strategies through comprehensive big data utilization. The study emphasizes developing effective preventive measures to enhance risk management in financial auditing [9].

T. Walker et al. note that the enhanced predictive capabilities of financial models combined with big data have driven innovations in automated lending, portfolio management (robo-advising), risk management, fraud detection, quantitative and high-frequency trading, as well as customer support. However, the authors identify critical unresolved issues including data collection methods (consumer privacy and ethical concerns), storage (environmental impact), security, and analytical utilization [10].

W. Han developed a model based on cloud technologies for analyzing the financial risk of an enterprise in the face of information growth. The author concludes this model improves risk assessment efficiency, accuracy, effectiveness, and security compared to traditional approaches [11].

K. Wang and Y. Chen developed a financial and economic monitoring system based on big data clustering. The authors demonstrating its capacity to reduce operational risks and promote balanced financial market development [12].

Big data applications in SMEs enhance decision-making, optimize business processes, improve marketing efficiency, and strengthen risk management.

M. Willetts and A. S. Atkins emphasize that only 10% of SMEs have adopted this technology despite benefits like improved efficiency and profitability. The authors identify a lack of measurable performance indicators to validate big data analytics' commercial value relative to IT investments for SMEs [13].

P. Q. Huy and V. K. Phuc analyze how big data and business intelligence capabilities provide a range of opportunities for SMEs to succeed in e-commerce [14].

M. Vachkova et al. examine the adoption rates of big data and predictive analytics among Malaysian micro, small and medium enterprises, recognizing these technologies' revolutionary potential for operational management [15].

The use of big data in various countries contributes to economic growth, improves government services, enhances business efficiency, and strengthens risk management, while accounting for legislative and technological specificities.

X. Wang notes that financial technology integration in the big data era creates new challenges. The author develops fintech risk indicators and proposes countermeasures to support China's stable fintech development [16].

R. Gul and M. A. S. Al-Faryan investigate the impact of data-driven decision-making on productivity, given the data analytics capabilities of Pakistan's banking sector. According to the authors, banks that use analytics and implement decision-making methods increase their productivity by 9-10% [17].

S. A. Sayed et al. propose big data solutions for addressing food security challenges in Egypt's agricultural sector [18].

T. Karaboga et al., based on a survey of 432 big data experts from 132 firms operating in Turkey, demonstrate that big data analytics management capabilities and a data-driven culture have a significant positive impact on both operational and financial performance of a firm. According to the authors, a data-driven culture largely mediates the relationships between big data analytics management capabilities and both operational and financial performance metrics [19].

M. C. Faruk et al. argue that the success of digital marketing depends on the proper utilization of insights derived from big data. However, a survey conducted among marketing managers in Bangladesh revealed that awareness of big data analytics mechanisms does not influence adoption intentions [20].

Big data enhances the competitiveness of companies by improving decision-making, personalizing services, and optimizing processes, while also strengthening reputation through increased transparency and customer trust.

M. P. Cristescu et al. explore the impact of big data analytics on corporate competitiveness. The research findings indicate a positive correlation between the percentage of companies utilizing big data analytics and the competitiveness index during 2018–2020 [21].

C. Li and M. Huang argue that leveraging big data and environmental sustainability can provide significant business benefits, including cost savings, higher productivity, and improved reputation. Big data in environmental monitoring enables better detection and resolution of sustainability challenges, including resource depletion, waste management, and air/water pollution. The authors emphasize that big data management requires a commitment to sustainability principles and practices, as well as a deep understanding of a company's or sector's environmental impact [22].

P. M. Kulkarni et al. address the challenges faced by data scientists and analysts employing big data models in the retail sector. The research identifies variables such as data security and data cost as effective during model deployment, while factors such as data privacy, reliability, and technological infrastructure proved to be ineffective [23].

F. Bandara et al. note that organizations integrate big data technologies with enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems to enhance the ability of ERP systems to handle large amounts of data. The authors identified 12 factors (for example, big data management and data contextualization) and their relationships that affect ERP responsiveness [24].

The literature review reveals that a significant number of researchers address challenges in data governance, ethics, and utilization, as well as the need for advancing information system platforms and standards. It is noted that the adoption of big data methods fosters innovation in lending, risk management, fraud prevention, and process automation. Additionally, challenges related to privacy, ethical considerations, and environmental implications are highlighted. Overall, big data usage improves the efficiency, accuracy, and security of financial operations but necessitates further advancements in technology and standards.

Thus, the existing theoretical approaches to utilizing big data in the financial sector were examined. This topic requires the collection and analysis of empirical data on how the use of big data affects financial institutions and financial stability.

RESULTS

Using Big Data in the financial sector

The digitalization of all sectors of the economy has predetermined rapid advancements in information technologies and big data, enabling faster and more comprehensive data analysis, improved decision-making, and higher-quality financial services for consumers. Despite the high relevance of big data applications in the economy, the primary focus in academic and business literature remains on the technological aspects of big data management and processing methods. Meanwhile, the economic implications of big data and their utilization from the perspective of economic potential receive less attention [25].

At the moment, the use of big data in the financial sector exhibits the following trends:

1. As mentioned earlier, the increasingly frequent use of big data technology and artificial intelligence for processing means that every second a considerable amount of new information is generated regarding the sale and purchase of goods and services, payment transactions, e-commerce, and other related activities. This actualizes the need to develop and implement Big Data technology for high-quality processing of this information.

Figure 1 Technology adoption rates across all financial segments [26]

Thus, according to the results of a survey of participants in the Russian financial sector, presented in Figure 1, big data ranks fifth in terms of adoption—Big Data technologies and big data analytics are employed by approximately half (46%) of the surveyed companies.

Big data analytics is more prevalent in banks than in insurance companies – the adoption rate of big data analytics technologies stands at 83% in banks compared to just 21% in insurance firms. The insurance industry as a whole lags in technology penetration, including big data analytics, machine learning, and related fields.

2. Smaller financial institutions relying on third-party big data solutions while large financial institutions develop in-house capabilities. Financial institutions are also increasingly adopting cloud technologies for machine learning data processing due to insufficient in-house server capacity [27]. A notable example of third-party technology adoption is the partnership between Germany's Deutsche Bank and Google Cloud to develop solutions leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence [Ibid.]. This provides the bank with advantages in streamlining risk management, cash flow forecasting, securities management, and other areas.
3. The use of alternative data sources by financial institutions, including social media, satellite data, real estate prices indices, media content, and other unconventional datasets. This big data application approach enables the use of information previously untapped for financial purposes. Such data proves valuable for securities trading, investment decisions, credit scoring, and similar applications.

According to a 2019 joint study by the University of Cambridge and the World Economic Forum, the most common alternative data sources in the financial sector include social media (used by 55% of surveyed companies), payment service provider data (49%), geolocation data (47%), application usage statistics (47%), news trends (44%), and satellite data (27%) [28].

Currently, big data technology has found widespread application in the financial sector:

1. Assessment of clients' creditworthiness – Evaluating the creditworthiness of clients and loan applicants requires processing substantial volumes of data generated and stored by financial institutions, as well as external data sources. Traditional screening methods reject approximately a quarter of potential borrowers due to insufficient initial deposits or low income levels. Big data

analytics enables not only financial profiling but also behavioral assessment—analyzing social media activity, personal traits, payment patterns, and transaction history. This approach helps predict default risks more accurately. For instance, Destacame utilizes alternative borrower data, including utility bill payments and income/expense flows, to assess repayment capacity [29].

2. Marketing and customer engagement – Big data analytics allows financial institutions to track customer preferences and deliver targeted, personalized product offerings. This enhances marketing efficiency by aligning promotions with individual needs. Additionally, financial firms leverage big data from customer interactions, complaints, and feedback to refine services.
3. Asset management – Big data tools optimize asset yields, facilitate investment portfolio construction, and enhance decision-making processes.
4. Insurance – Insurance companies increasingly adopt big data analytics to streamline claims processing, detect fraud, develop business models, refine pricing strategies, and forecast sales trends.
5. Operational risk mitigation – Big data analysis identifies fraudulent activities and suspicious transactions, helping prevent financial crimes.
6. Reporting and process optimization – Big data automates regulatory reporting, trade finance transaction monitoring, profit/loss statement generation, and workforce productivity analysis.

Consequently, the financial sector will likely witness further expansion of big data applications and deeper integration of related technologies into both internal and external processes.

Benefits of using Big Data in financial institutions

Based on current practices in big data applications and analytics technologies in Russia and abroad, N.P. Kozlova [30], N.N. Martynenko, E.O. Kotova [31], Sh.G.U. Niyazbekova [32], and Jun Gao [33] identify several key advantages of these technologies.

First, the high speed of data processing – this characteristic enables big data analytics technologies to rapidly extract relevant information from various external and internal sources, facilitating prompt decision-making.

Second, the application of big data, artificial intelligence, and machine learning in finance enhances risk management quality by analyzing and identifying customer behavioral patterns that traditional tools cannot detect. Big data-driven scoring enables the development of fairer pricing models that better balance risk and profitability. Artificial intelligence technologies also help detect and mitigate cyber risks.

Third, since big data analytics incorporates diverse alternative customer data, including beyond just income and bank account information, it improves financial product accessibility. Big data helps expand the customer base by including households and small businesses that lack credit history but demonstrate significant potential.

Fourth, through comprehensive and multifaceted analysis of customer preferences and behavioral patterns, financial institutions can deliver personalized services and offers tailored to individual needs and desires. This is particularly important for millennials, who value customized approaches.

Survey results indicate that the main advantages of big data technologies for financial sector organizations include improved risk management quality and efficiency, business process optimization, expanded customer base, and increased accessibility of financial services and products for the public.

However, despite all the advantages and potential for application in the financial sector, big data technologies present certain challenges and drawbacks. Market participants in financial services highlight the following issues [34]:

- Shortage of technological expertise and skilled personnel in big data creation and management. The implementation and use of modern technologies such as big data require highly qualified specialists and continuous training, which is challenging due to the lack of industry-wide practices and standards. Despite the growing popularity of IT-related professions, demand for specialists in this field still exceeds supply. Beyond the financial sector, IT professionals are also in high demand in IT companies, large retail chains, healthcare institutions, and other industries;
- Insufficient development of regulatory and legal frameworks concerning the implementation and use of big data, as well as technologies and methods for processing them in financial institutions;
- Currently, there is a lack of data in Russia on real-world applications of big data and methodologies for assessing their effectiveness in the financial sector. This

is because financial institutions have only recently begun adopting big data, and domestic companies have not yet accumulated sufficient analytical data on the effectiveness, advantages, drawbacks, and risks associated with these technologies;

- Insufficient quality of data and algorithms. For machine learning systems, there are currently no standardized methods for verifying the reliability and security of algorithms;
- Lack of regulation for financial services in the areas of artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things (IoT). Due to these “gray zones”, risks emerge that could negatively impact the security of financial institutions [35].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of scientific literature on the research topic, considering the presented definitions and advantages of big data, the authors of the study propose another definition of big data technology in the financial sector: it represents significant volumes of information assets stored in internal and external sources, for whose transformation, processing and analysis specialized technologies and methods are used. These enable identifying trends in financial institution customers' behavior, conducting scoring, detecting and preventing cyber risks, improving risk management efficiency, creating personalized financial product and service offerings, optimizing business processes, expanding customer base, and increasing organizational profitability.

Big Data is not just another technology for financial institutions; it represents a promising direction for developing and improving both internal operations and external activities. It allows enhancing customer relationships and loyalty, reducing risks, and improving the efficiency of financial product and service delivery. Currently, one of the most critical issues is preparing the platform and infrastructure for implementing big data, artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, training qualified personnel, and addressing legislative gaps.

In conclusion, several advantages of utilizing big data in the financial sector should be highlighted. The use of big data allows financial institutions to streamline processes, reduce costs, and increase the speed of information processing. Big data analysis enables the identification of potential risks and threats, allowing financial institutions to develop more effective risk management strategies. Big data unlocks

new possibilities for creating personalized financial products and services tailored to the specific needs of individual customers. Utilizing big data enables the development of more sophisticated and efficient algorithms to detect and prevent fraud. Financial institutions can utilize big data to collect and analyze the information necessary to comply with regulatory requirements. Big data analysis enables financial institutions to anticipate market trends and changes, allowing them to adapt to new conditions and make data-driven decisions.

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INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Fedor O. Chernenkov	Graduate Student. Moscow Financial and Industrial University Synergy (Russia, Moscow). E-mail: atlz77777@yandex.ru. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-7340-3527	Writing - Original Draft, Visualization
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Omer Allagabo Omer Mustafa	PhD in Economics, Assistant Professor of Economics, Banking and Finance. Sudan Academy for Banking and Financial Sciences (Sudan, Omdurman). E-mail: omergabo78@sabfs.edu.sd. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1697-8877	Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing
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